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Development of a Mechanically Regenerating Desublimator for Freeze-Drying Systems in the Food Industry

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ABSTRACT

Mechanical regeneration of desublimator heat-exchanger surfaces is proposed as an energy- and cost-efficient alternative to steam defrosting in industrial freeze dryers. A pilot-scale mechanically regenerated desublimator (MRD) was designed, built, and tested under food-drying conditions. Continuous scraping keeps the overall heat-transfer coefficient at the clean-surface level and avoids warm-up/cool-down cycles. Compared with a thermally regenerated desublimator (TRD), the specific energy for desublimating 1 kg H₂O decreased from 923 to 820 Wh kg⁻¹ (−11.2%). The required energy for scraping was 35 Wh kg⁻¹ of frost, which is approximately three times lower than the minimum latent heat input required for thermal defrosting. One MRD can replace two TRDs operating in an alternating cycle, reducing investment costs and enabling continuous freeze-drying.

1 | Introduction

1.1 | Background

Drying is an energy-intensive process, employed across various sectors and accounting for 10%–20% of total industrial energy consumption in most developed countries [1]. The main reason for the high energy demand is the need to supply the latent heat of evaporation to remove water or other solvents.

In agriculture, drying helps to preserve crops and prevent spoilage. The pharmaceutical sector relies on it to ensure the stability and efficacy of drugs. In the chemical industry, compounds such as polymers and resins are dried to aid processing. Food processing benefits from drying by extending the shelf life and reducing the weight of products, such as milk powder, coffee, and snacks. The textile industry removes moisture from fibers to improve usability. Similarly, in the construction industry,

materials, such as bricks, tiles, and cement, are dried to improve durability and performance.

In the food industry, common drying methods include convective drying (e.g., hot air drying for fruits and vegetables, spray drying for milk powder and instant coffee), contact drying (e.g., drum drying for potato flakes), dielectric drying (e.g., microwave drying for herbs and snacks), and lyophilization, also known as vacuum freeze-drying (for berries and ready-to-eat meals). Convective dryers dominate industrial practice, with over 85% of installations utilizing hot air or combustion gases as the heat-transfer medium [2]. Among these methods, lyophilization stands out for its ability to preserve product quality, albeit at higher cost and energy demand.

To enhance process economics, reduce energy consumption, and lower carbon footprints, the development of more efficient drying systems is essential.

Abbreviations: MRD, mechanically regenerated desublimator; TRD, thermally regenerated desublimator.

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FIGURE 1 | p,T -diagram for H_2O with equilibrium curves and triple points [3]. CP, critical point.

The relevant drying process for the work presented here is lyophilization, which is a dehydration method based on sublimation. For this to occur, a substance must transition directly from the solid phase to the gas phase at a pressure below its triple point. For H_2O , this point is at a pressure of 0.611 kPa (6.11 mbar(a)) and a temperature of 273.16 K (0.01°C), as shown in Figure 1. Below this pressure, H_2O can only exist in the gaseous or solid phase.

The drying process in lyophilization consists of two periods: during the primary drying period, the bulk of the solvent (mostly H_2O), predominantly in the form of crystals, is removed through sublimation. However, some solvent might remain in an amorphous state, not forming crystals. In the secondary drying period, any remaining solvent, which is bound to the product's structure and thus did not crystallize, is removed by desorption [4].

Owing to its low process temperatures and the absence of liquid phases, lyophilization is comparably gentle among other drying methods and is often chosen when preserving the physical and chemical quality characteristics of a product is paramount [5].

Lyophilization can be segmented into four primary operations: freezing the product, evacuating the drying chamber, drying the product (sublimation and desorption), and removing the vapor from the drying chamber.

Under the low-pressure conditions within the drying chamber, the resulting vapors occupy a substantial volume—1 kg of water vapor at a pressure of 0.5 mbar(a) extends to a volume of approximately 2270 m^3 —making its extraction via vacuum pumps highly energy-intensive. A more economical approach involves directing the vapor through a desublimator—often, and strictly speaking incorrectly, referred to as a “condenser” when operating below water’s triple point—whose heat exchanger cools the vapor until it desublimates into frost.

The higher temperature at the sublimation front of the material to be dried, compared to the lower temperature at the desublimation front on the cooled heat exchanger surface within the desublimator, results in a higher solvent partial pressure in the drying chamber compared to the desublimator. This pressure difference serves as the driving force for the convective vapor transport from the drying chamber to the desublimator.

As desublimation progresses, frost builds up on the heat exchanger surface, which not only reduces the available flow area within the desublimator, but also likely impairs the heat transfer, thereby reducing the efficiency of the refrigeration system.

In batch production, these deteriorations are often accepted until the process concludes, with the heat exchanger being regenerated (defrosted) between batches.

In a semi-continuous lyophilization process, however, regeneration must occur periodically during operation.

Regeneration techniques include the following [6]:

- Defrosting with steam, utilizing superheated steam to thaw the frost.
- Electrical defrosting, with electric heaters melting away the frost.
- Hot gas defrosting, involving the circulation of hot refrigerant gas through the heat exchanger.
- Radiation defrosting, employing microwaves or infrared to selectively melt frost layers.
- Chemical defrosting, using chemical agents to dissolve the frost buildup.

- Mechanical defrosting, where frost is physically removed via scraping or brushing.

Although the concept of mechanical defrosting was mentioned as early as 1978 [6], Kröll describes it merely as a conceived idea (“erdacht”) for continuous freeze-drying operations, without providing implementation details or performance data. Historical patents from the late 1950s and early 1960s describe scraper-condenser units for the recovery of various sublimable materials, such as iodine, sulfur, and phthalic anhydride [7, 8], but these were designed for general chemical processing applications, not for the specific requirements of food freeze-drying—namely, high vacuum below the triple point of water, cryogenic temperatures, and food-grade hygiene standards. There is no evidence of commercialization or published performance evaluations for any of these concepts. A comprehensive literature review confirms that no mechanical defrosting system for vacuum freeze-dryer condensers has been brought to market to date, nor have quantitative performance data for such systems been published. Existing scraped-surface heat exchanger technology, well-established in atmospheric applications, such as ice cream freezers and crystallizers [9], operates exclusively at atmospheric pressure and cannot be directly transferred to vacuum conditions below the triple point of water. The industry standard for continuous freeze-drying remains thermal defrosting using dual alternating condensers (e.g., GEA’s CDI technology [10]), which requires duplicate condenser hardware. The present work provides, to the authors’ knowledge, the first experimental performance data for a mechanically regenerated desublimator (MRD) operating under food freeze-drying conditions.

Depending on the process specifics, the energy demand of the desublimator accounts for approximately 20%–30% of the total energy demand of the lyophilization system [11–13]. In thermally regenerated systems, a significant proportion of this energy, ranging from 20% to 40%, is used for regeneration, with the remainder supporting cooling for desublimation.

Lyophilization is often regarded as a costly drying technique. Its energy requirement is roughly double that of convective drying methods, with process times also being considerably extended [7]. When compared to air-drying, the costs for freeze-drying are four to eight times higher [9].

Due to the substantial equipment needs, investment costs for lyophilization are considerable, where the desublimation system alone can make up about 30% of the total system cost. Given its substantial impact on the overall economics, there are ongoing efforts to minimize the expenses associated with the desublimation system.

This push towards cost-effectiveness aligns with a growing market demand. Lyophilized products are expected to be increasingly sought-after across the food and pharmaceutical industries [14–16].

1.2 | Goals

The aim of this project was to develop an innovative desublimation system for lyophilization, compatible with both semi-

FIGURE 2 | Pilot-scale lyophilization plant at Bucher Unipektin AG, Niederweningen/Switzerland (without desublimator).

continuous belt drying systems and batch drying cabinets. The design focuses on modularity, improved energy efficiency, and reducing operating costs below current industry benchmarks. Success in these areas could deliver significant economic and environmental benefits.

2 | Prototype and Experiments

To enhance the understanding of the physical and technical processes involved, a detailed theoretical and experimental study was undertaken on a pilot-scale lyophilization system installed at Bucher Unipektin AG, as illustrated in Figure 2. The system incorporates a desublimator featuring a tubular heat exchanger, which is periodically regenerated through thermal defrosting using superheated steam. Figure 3 provides the visual documentation of the heat exchanger tubes of this desublimator in three distinct states: prior to operation, during the desublimation process, and following its completion. The structural characteristics of the frost layer are critically dependent on the process parameters. Under optimized conditions, the frost layer exhibits a smooth and dense morphology, which facilitates superior heat transfer dynamics by minimizing thermal resistance at the frost–heat exchanger interface. Conversely, suboptimal conditions, particularly elevated pressures resulting from insufficient evacuation of permanent and leakage gases, lead to the formation of a porous, snow-like frost structure. Such a morphology significantly impairs thermal conductivity, thereby reducing the efficiency of the cooling process.

After delineating the sub-functions of the desublimator system, a series of partial technical solutions were systematically structured within a morphological matrix. This matrix became the foundation for conceptual development, resulting in five distinct designs. These concepts underwent a comprehensive utility analysis to evaluate their technical feasibility and operational performance. The utility analysis was based on a robust and balanced set of criteria, among which the most critical were as follows:

- Energy efficiency: Comparison of heating and cooling demands in relation to the quantity of water desublimated.
- Manufacturability: Consideration of fabrication complexity and associated costs.

FIGURE 3 | Heat exchanger of the thermally regenerated desublimator in the pilot-scale system at Bucher Unipektin AG. Far left: prior to the desublimation process; center left: during desublimation; and center right and right: after the completion of the desublimation process.

- Operational costs: Analysis of the expenses incurred during system operation.
- Reliability and vacuum integrity: Ensuring system robustness and the ability to maintain vacuum conditions effectively.
- Process adaptability: Suitability for both continuous drying processes (e.g., belt dryers) and batch processes (e.g., drying chambers).
- Scalability and modularity: Adaptability to different vapor flow rates, including the ability to scale up or combine multiple units.

Following the utility analysis, the concept of “mechanical regeneration by scraping” emerged as the most advantageous and was therefore selected for further development. A schematic representation of the concept can be seen in Figure 4.

Consequently, a prototype of an MRD was designed and constructed to serve as an experimental testbed, see Figure 5. This prototype incorporates a precision-engineered scraper mechanism that traverses along the tubes of a bundle-configured heat exchanger, removing frost accumulation. The detached frost is subsequently collected and expelled from the desublimator through an integrated sluice system, ensuring continuous operation.

A challenge identified is the potential for mechanical wear on both the scraper mechanism and the heat exchanger tubes. Various design strategies were utilized to create a robust system with minimal deformations and to ensure a uniform distribution of mechanical stress. These approaches were aimed at enhancing both the durability and longevity of the system.

The prototype’s functionality was effectively validated through testing. The operations of scraping frost and its subsequent discharge were executed without significant issues. However, an increase in system pressure was observed during the scraping process. This was caused by frost particles accumulating and sublimating on the warmer airlock flap. Although this pressure

rise was within acceptable limits, it indicated potential for improvement through cooling the flaps. The energy consumption of the drive unit for mechanical regeneration was, as expected, relatively low, averaging approximately 125 kJ or 35 Wh kg⁻¹ of removed frost.

3 | Performance Indicators

In order to evaluate and compare the efficiency of various desublimators, relevant characteristic values are proposed below.

3.1 | Coefficient of Performance COP_{desub}

The coefficient of performance (COP) of a desublimator system can be defined as the ratio of the **desublimation enthalpy**—representing the benefit or the useful effect—to the **energy consumption**—the total energy input required by the desublimator and its auxiliary systems to achieve the desublimation:

$$\text{COP}_{\text{desub}} = \frac{H}{E_d} = \frac{m_D \Delta h_s}{E_d} \quad [-]$$

with

- H is the desublimation enthalpy per cycle [J].
- E_d is the energy consumption for desublimator per cycle [J].
- m_D is the desublimated mass per cycle [kg].
- Δh_s is the specific sublimation enthalpy [J kg⁻¹].

The energy consumption E_d is made up as follows:

$$E_d = E_{d,c,\alpha} + E_{d,c,\beta} + Q_{\text{reg}} \quad [\text{J}] \quad \text{thermal regeneration}$$

$$E_d = E_{d,c,\alpha} + E_{d,c,\beta} + E_{d,m} + E_{d,s} \quad [\text{J}] \quad \text{mechanical regeneration}$$

with

FIGURE 4 | Schematic representation of a mechanically regenerated desublimation system.

FIGURE 5 | Prototype of the mechanically regenerated desublimator at Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts, Horw, Switzerland. (1) Pressure and temperature sensors; (2) mechanical scraper; (3) heat exchanger tubes; (4) sluice system; (5) vacuum pump; (6) control and monitoring; (7) drive unit with gearbox for scraper; (8) cooling system for heat exchanger; (9) cooling system for hopper before sluice, and (10) steam generation.

- $E_{d,c,\alpha}$ is the energy consumption for cooling before desublimation.
- $E_{d,c,\beta}$ is the energy consumption for cooling during desublimation.
- Q_{reg} is the energy consumption for thermal regeneration.
- $E_{d,m}$ is the energy consumption for mechanical regeneration.
- $E_{d,s}$ is the energy consumption for the sluice system.

3.2 | Specific Energy Demand E_{desub}

The specific energy demand is the energy required by the desublimator and its auxiliaries to desublimates 1 kg of vapor.

$$E_{\text{desub}} = \frac{E_d}{m_D} = \frac{\Delta h_s}{\text{COP}_{\text{desub}}} [\text{J kg}^{-1}]$$

3.3 | Specific Operational Expenditure $\text{opex}_{\text{desub}}$

The specific operational expenditure refers to the energy costs required to desublimates 1 kg of vapor:

$$\text{opex}_{\text{desub}} = \frac{K_O}{m_D} [\text{€ kg}^{-1}]$$

with

- K_O is the energy costs per cycle [€].

4 | Key Parameters

4.1 | Density and Thermal Conductivity λ_f of the Frost

The cooling load and regeneration frequency of a desublimator are dependent on the density and effective thermal conductivity of the accumulating frost layer. The microstructure of frost produced on a desublimator, and thus its effective thermal conductivity, is governed primarily by the local mass- and heat-flux conditions—mechanisms that remain an active field of research [17]. A large temperature difference ΔT between the drying product and the cooled desublimator surface drives a high sublimation rate and, consequently, a vigorous vapor flow. The ensuing bombardment of the cold desublimator surface by H_2O vapor molecules creates numerous nuclei, which develop into highly branched, fine-crystalline dendrites, forming a loose, felt-like layer with high porosity. When ΔT (and hence the sublimation rate) decreases, fewer nuclei form; they grow more slowly, coalesce, and densify, producing a more compact frost layer with markedly higher thermal conductivity. Cryomicroscopic (in situ imaging) observations and numerical simulations further show that a fraction of the water vapor penetrates the porous deposit and condenses on internal surfaces, thereby increasing density [18].

Laboratory trials with the HSLU prototype, operated at a desublimation flux j_{sub} of $1.5 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ (defined as the mass flow rate of vapor per hour and per square meter of heat-exchanger surface

FIGURE 6 | Frost particles generated in the HSLU laboratory, collected after mechanical scraping and discharge from the desublimator.

area), a pressure of 100 Pa, and a frost-surface temperature of $\approx -42^\circ\text{C}$, generated a dense, ice-like layer (Figure 6). Comparable behavior was reported by NASA (2023), which observed that frost grown at 200–500 Pa attained densities slightly above those of deposits formed at atmospheric pressure [17]. In the present study, a reference ice density of 917 kg m^{-3} was adopted.

Depending on its porosity, the effective thermal conductivity λ_f of the frost ranges from about $0.02 \text{ W (m K)}^{-1}$, a value close to that of moist air, up to roughly 2.0 W (m K)^{-1} , which is typical for ice [19]. Haseley and Oetjen [4, p. 196] recommend a value for λ_f of $1.75 \text{ W (m K)}^{-1}$ for smooth, virtually pore-free layers, which is also used in the work at hand.

4.2 | External Heat-Transfer Coefficient α_e

The external heat-transfer coefficient α_e is primarily governed by the prevailing flow regime (laminar, transitional, or turbulent) that develops along the frosted surface.

The flow regime itself responds to changes in vapor mass flux, system pressure, fluid properties dictated by frost-surface temperature, and surface geometry. Consequently, α_e is not a material constant but a dynamic parameter linking these operating conditions to the sensible and latent heat transferred from the water-vapor stream to the growing frost layer.

Prototype measurements at HSLU yielded $\alpha_e \approx 50 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$ under near-laminar conditions: The test cell had a very high void-to-area ratio $V/A \approx 0.8$ (0.8 m^3 free volume per m^2 of heat-exchanger surface) and a low desublimation flux j_{sub} of $1.50 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-2}$. Industrial desublimators typically operate with vapor mass fluxes two to five times higher and V/A ratios below 0.1, generating turbulent flow regimes and therefore higher heat-transfer coefficients. A review of recent freeze-dryer brochures indicates an α_e in the range of $80\text{--}140 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$. In the following calculations, a mid-range value of $110 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$ is adopted as the design basis.

FIGURE 7 | Overall heat-transfer coefficient k as a function of frost-layer thickness for a smooth stainless-steel tube ($d = 30$ mm). Results are shown for different external convective heat-transfer coefficients, $\alpha_e = 60$ – 120 $\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$ (desublimating steam side), and two frost thermal conductivities, $\lambda_f = 0.75$ W (m K)^{-1} and 1.75 W (m K)^{-1} .

4.3 | Process Parameters

For benchmarking, a thermally regenerated freeze-drying line equipped with two alternating desublimators—model RAY 75 from GEA [10]—was selected as the reference system. According to the manufacturer’s brochure, this unit achieves a nominal dehydration capacity of 1550 kg of H_2O in 24 h. Using a **specific sublimation enthalpy** of 2989 kJ kg^{-1} (2656 kJ kg^{-1} enthalpy of evaporation at -50°C , calculated with the PPDS-equation [20, p. 154] and 333 kJ kg^{-1} enthalpy of fusion [21]), the corresponding continuous heat load on the desublimator heat exchanger is roughly 54 kW . In the present analysis, the heat load was rounded to **50 kW**, paired with a corresponding desublimation rate of 60 kg h^{-1} . The brochure also states that the frost layer on the heat-exchanger surfaces must not exceed 5 mm; once this thickness is reached, the desublimator is defrosted. Assuming the limit is attained after about 1 h of operation, an assumed **shell-and-tube bundle with 30 mm tube outer diameter** requires an overall heat-transfer surface of approximately 11.2 m^2 to sustain continuous production under these conditions.

The acceptable **chamber pressure** during primary drying is dictated by the product-specific collapse or glass transition temperature. For most dried plant matrices, this range is 0.63 – 1.24 mbar (63 – 124 Pa); however, protein- or sugar-rich pharmaceutical formulations tolerate only 0.05 – 0.20 mbar (5 – 20 Pa) [22]. In the present study, an upper limit of **0.10 mbar** was adopted; lower pressures are permissible, provided that they do not exceed this threshold. At 0.10 mbar, the equilibrium ice sublimation temperature is -42.2°C ; consequently, the desublimator’s **frost layer surface temperature** must not exceed this temperature. The **temperature** of the incoming **water-vapor** stream was fixed at -20°C . Furthermore, it was assumed that the desublimator contains a thermal mass of 125 kg stainless steel and 83 kg of the refrigerant R410A. Prior to each operation, both must be cooled down from 0°C to -62.5°C .

Under these conditions, the mean free path of water vapor molecules is on the order of 1 mm. With a minimum gap between heat exchanger tubes of approximately 70 mm, the Knudsen number is $Kn \approx 0.015$, confirming that the flow remains in the

continuum regime ($Kn < 0.1$). Molecular (Knudsen) flow effects can therefore be neglected. The Reynolds number is in the order of $Re \approx 500$, indicating laminar flow.

4.4 | Vacuum Pump

It was assumed that the energy required by the vacuum pump to evacuate a given volume can be calculated using the thermodynamic principles for ideal gases. The work W needed for isothermal evacuation of a gas volume from an initial pressure P_1 to a final pressure P_2 at a constant temperature is expressed by the following relation:

$$W = P_1 \cdot V \cdot \ln \left(\frac{P_1}{P_2} \right)$$

An **efficiency** of **15%** was assumed for the vacuum pump operation. The initial condition P_1 corresponds to standard atmospheric pressure, P_2 was set to 0.1 mbar (as described above). The **volume** V of the desublimator to be evacuated was defined as **0.30 m³**. Additionally, the energy demand of the vacuum pump operating at P_2 was specified with **3.3 kW**, based on technical data provided by the manufacturer Busch (rotary-vane vacuum pump R5 RA 0205 D).

5 | Results

5.1 | Overall Heat-Transfer Coefficient k

To calculate the required evaporation temperatures of the refrigerant on the inner side of the heat exchanger, the overall heat-transfer coefficient k must be determined first. The larger k is, the higher the permissible evaporation temperature on the refrigerant side, which in turn improves the refrigeration system’s efficiency. k is strongly governed by the frost-layer thickness, the thermal conductivity of the frost λ_f , and the convective heat-transfer coefficient α_e from vapor to frost.

A maybe counterintuitive result is observed for $\lambda_f = 1.75$ W (m K)^{-1} and $\alpha_e \leq 100$ $\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$: As the frost layer grows, k increases

FIGURE 8 | Thermal impact of frost-layer growth for high-conductivity frost ($\lambda_f = 1.75 \text{ W (m K)}^{-1}$). All diagrams show the respective quantity as a function of frost-layer thickness δ_f . (a) Inner tube wall temperature ϑ_i , (b) frost-surface temperature ϑ_e , and (c) specific electrical energy $e_{c,\beta}$ required to desublimiate 1 kg H_2O . (d) Inner tube wall temperature ϑ_i , (e) frost-surface temperature ϑ_e , and (f) specific electrical energy $e_{c,\beta}$ required to desublimiate 1 kg H_2O , evaluated under the constraints $\vartheta_e < -42^\circ\text{C}$ and $\vartheta_i > -85^\circ\text{C}$.

before reaching its maximum value and then starts to decrease (Figure 7, left side). This behavior is attributed to the enlargement of the active heat-transfer area caused by the expanding frost and can occur in configurations with comparatively low α_e values. If λ_f is reduced to $0.75 \text{ W (m K)}^{-1}$, the effect vanishes (Figure 7, right side).

5.2 | Impact of Frost-Layer Growth on Temperatures and Specific Energy Demand During Desublimation

Figure 8 shows the influence of frost growth on the thermal performance of the desublimator with a λ_f of $1.75 \text{ W (m K)}^{-1}$.

FIGURE 9 | Thermal impact of frost-layer growth for low-conductivity frost ($\lambda_f = 0.75 \text{ W (m K)}^{-1}$). All diagrams show the respective quantity as a function of frost-layer thickness δ_f . (a) Inner tube wall temperature ϑ_i , (b) frost-surface temperature ϑ_e , and (c) specific electrical energy $e_{c,\beta}$ required to desublimite 1 kg H_2O . (d) Inner tube wall temperature ϑ_i , (e) frost-surface temperature ϑ_e , and (f) specific electrical energy $e_{c,\beta}$ required to desublimite 1 kg H_2O , evaluated under the constraints $\vartheta_e < -42^\circ C$ and $\vartheta_i > -85^\circ C$.

Diagrams (a)–(c) show the inner tube wall temperature ϑ_i , frost-surface temperature ϑ_e and $e_{c,\beta}$ required to desublimite 1 kg of H_2O , whereas a constant heat duty of 50 kW is maintained.

The specific electrical energy values correspond to the mean cumulative electrical work input accumulated as the frost layer δ_f thickens from 0 mm to the indicated mass. Because frost growth

slows with increasing layer thickness and the inner-wall temperature of the desublimator drifts accordingly, the instantaneous COP of the refrigeration unit was integrated along the growth trajectory to obtain a representative aggregate value. Refrigeration is supplied by a compression heat pump operating at a second-law efficiency $\eta = 0.50$ and rejecting heat at a condenser temperature of $30^\circ C$.

FIGURE 10 | Specific energy demand breakdown for a thermally regenerated desublimator (TRD) and a mechanically regenerated desublimator (MRD), $e_{c,\alpha}$: cooling before desublimation, $e_{c,\beta}$: cooling during desublimation, $e_{v,\alpha}$: vacuuming prior to desublimation, $e_{v,\beta}$: vacuuming during desublimation, q_{reg} : thermal regeneration, e_{reg} : mechanical regeneration.

Diagrams (d)–(f) repeat the analysis under the limits: $\vartheta_i \geq -85^\circ\text{C}$ and $\vartheta_e \leq 42^\circ\text{C}$ (corresponding saturation pressure of 0.1 mbar). Curves for $\alpha_e = 60$ and $50 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$ are omitted because these settings violate at least one temperature constraint within the explored frost-thickness range.

Figure 9 provides the same analysis for a lower frost thermal conductivity of $\lambda_f = 0.75 \text{ W (m K)}^{-1}$; only curves satisfying the temperature limits appear in diagrams (d)–(f).

5.3 | Specific Energy Demand and Performance Indicators

Figure 10 compares the specific energy demand of a thermally regenerated desublimator (TRD) with that of an MRD for a 24 h production cycle handling $1440 \text{ kg H}_2\text{O}$ (60 kg h^{-1}). Assuming two alternating TRD modules that can each accommodate 60 kg of frost (5 mm frost layer thickness) before regeneration is needed and assuming the MRD is constantly regenerated and therefore operated at a frost layer thickness of 0 mm .

- $e_{c,\alpha}$ is the specific electrical energy to cool the thermal mass of the desublimator before the first desublimation and after every regeneration (TRD) [Wh kg^{-1}].

- $e_{c,\beta}$ is the specific electrical energy for cooling during desublimation [Wh kg^{-1}].
- $e_{v,\alpha}$ is the specific electrical energy for evacuating the vessel prior to the first desublimation step and after each regeneration (TRD) [Wh kg^{-1}].
- $e_{v,\beta}$ is the specific electrical energy to maintain the target pressure during desublimation [Wh kg^{-1}].
- q_{reg} (TRD)/ e_{reg} (MRD) is the specific energy required for regeneration; for the TRD this corresponds to the enthalpy of fusion (333 kJ kg^{-1}), for the MRD, the value was derived from measurements taken during prototype testing [Wh kg^{-1}].

Figure 10 shows that the specific energy demand e_{desub} for the TRD amounts to 923.5 and 820 Wh kg^{-1} for the MRD, reflecting a 11.2% reduction in energy consumption. Therefore, the COP for desublimation COP_{DESUB} was found to be 0.90 for the TRD and 1.01 for the MRD.

In both systems, the dominant contribution is $e_{c,\beta}$, which accounts for 79% (733 Wh kg^{-1}) of e_{desub} in the TRD and 89% (729 Wh kg^{-1}) in the MRD, highlighting the strong influence of the refrigeration system. The energy for regeneration of the TRD q_{reg}

is almost three times higher (92.5 Wh kg^{-1}) than e_{reg} for the MRD (34.2 Wh kg^{-1}). The markedly lower $e_{c,\alpha}$ and $e_{v,\alpha}$ of the MRD (1.4 and 0.4 Wh kg^{-1}) result from cooling and evacuating its desublimator only once per production cycle. However, the energy required to operate the MRD's airlock has been excluded from the analysis.

Assuming an electricity tariff of $26.5 \text{ ct (€) kWh}^{-1}$ [23], the specific operational expenditures $\text{opex}_{\text{desub}}$ are 24.5 ct kg^{-1} for the TRD and 21.7 ct kg^{-1} for the MRD.

6 | Discussion of Results

At high heat-transfer conditions ($\lambda_f = 1.75 \text{ W (m K)}^{-1}$, $\alpha_e = 110 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$), the cooling energy during desublimation, $e_{c,\beta}$, differs only slightly between the two concepts because the specific desublimation energy e_{sub} changes marginally when the frost layer thickness increases from 0 mm (MRD) to 5 mm (TRD), see Figure 8.

When the thermal resistance of the frost layer rises to $\lambda_f = 0.75 \text{ W (m K)}^{-1}$ and the external heat-transfer coefficient drops to $\alpha_e = 80 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$, the impact becomes pronounced:

- TRD: $e_{c,\beta} = 1002 \text{ Wh kg}^{-1}$
- MRD: $e_{c,\beta} = 914 \text{ Wh kg}^{-1}$

Consequently, the coefficient of performance $\text{COP}_{\text{desub}}$ for the TRD falls to 0.70 , whereas the MRD still achieves 0.83 , a 19% higher value than the TRD.

These results underline the strong dependence of overall desublimator efficiency on the external heat-transfer coefficient α_e and the frost thermal conductivity λ_f . Because mechanical regeneration continuously removes frost, keeping the layer at a minimum, the MRD largely decouples performance from unfavorable λ_f values and thus maintains superior energy efficiency.

The specific energy demand for mechanical regeneration e_{reg} was determined experimentally during prototype testing. Ongoing refinements to the scraper mechanism are expected to reduce this demand further. However, as unavoidable heat-transfer losses increase the required thermal input, the assumed energy demand of the TRD (q_{reg}) is likely to exceed the latent enthalpy of fusion. This increases the MRD's energetic advantage over the TRD, while simultaneously reducing the specific cost of sublimation. Continuous regeneration also enables a single MRD to replace the conventional pair of alternating TRDs, reducing capital expenditure and facilitating continuous freeze-drying.

7 | Summary and Outlook

The concept of a "MRD" has shown substantial promise in significantly reducing energy consumption, a vital consideration in industrial settings where efficiency is key. Its validation through a production-scale prototype confirms its viability for large-scale implementations, indicating that this innovative technology can

operate effectively not just in theoretical or small-scale scenarios, but also in real-world industrial applications.

A major advantage of this technology lies in its capability to facilitate continuous freeze-drying with just one desublimator, dramatically lowering capital costs. This feature makes it an appealing choice for industries aiming to enhance both operational performance and cost-effectiveness.

Furthermore, there are additional avenues for energy optimization. For instance, the scraped frost from the desublimator could be repurposed to meet cooling needs.

Looking ahead, Bucher Unipektin AG's consideration for commercializing this technology offers a hopeful path for its broader implementation.

Nomenclature

Symbols

$\text{COP}_{\text{desub}}$	coefficient of performance for desublimation, –
$e_{c,\alpha}$	specific electrical energy to cool the thermal mass of the desublimator before the first desublimation step, Wh kg^{-1}
$e_{c,\beta}$	specific electrical energy required to desublimator 1 kg of H_2O , J kg^{-1}
$e_{c,\beta}$	specific electrical energy for cooling during the desublimation phase, Wh kg^{-1}
e_{desub}	specific energy demand required by the desublimator and its auxiliaries to desublimator 1 kg of vapor, J kg^{-1}
e_{reg}	specific electrical energy required for mechanical regeneration, Wh kg^{-1}
$e_{v,\alpha}$	specific electrical energy for evacuating the vessel prior to desublimation step, Wh kg^{-1}
$e_{v,\beta}$	specific electrical energy to maintain the target pressure during desublimation, Wh kg^{-1}
\dot{j}_{sub}	resublimation flux; mass flow rate of vapor per hour and per square meter of heat-exchanger surface area, $\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$
k	overall heat-transfer coefficient of the desublimator (including the frost layer), W (m K)^{-1}
$\text{opex}_{\text{desub}}$	specific operational expenditure: describes the energy costs required to desublimator 1 kg of vapor, € kg^{-1}
q_{reg}	specific thermal energy required for regeneration, Wh kg^{-1}
V/A	free volume in desublimator per m^2 of heat-exchanger surface, m
α_e	external heat-transfer coefficient from the vapor onto the frost surface, $\text{W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$
ϑ_e	frost-surface temperature, $^\circ\text{C}$
ϑ_i	inner tube wall temperature, $^\circ\text{C}$
λ_f	effective thermal conductivity of the frost, W (m K)^{-1}

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Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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